

Kinetics and mechanism of uncatalyzed and silver(I) catalyzed oxidation of lysine by cerium(IV) in acid perchlorate medium

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Abstract : The kinetics of the uncatalyzed and silver(I) catalyzed oxidation of lysine with cerium(IV) has been studied in perchloric acid medium. The reaction is second order, that is first order with respect to each reactant. The mode of electron transfer has been indicated through an adduct between Ag^I and lysine via oxygen atom of the carboxyl group rather than the amino group. Uncatalyzed reaction simultaneously occurs with the silver(I) catalyzed reaction and the following rate law conforms to all experimental data observed in the reaction,

$$k = \frac{k_1[\text{H}^+]}{K_h + [\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_2[\text{Ag}^I][\text{H}^+]}{K_h + [\text{H}^+]}$$

where, k is an observed second order rate constant. A reaction mechanism accounting for all these experimental observations has been suggested.

Keywords : Lysine, cerium(IV), silver(I), perchloric acid.

Introduction

The oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids is of importance both from a photochemical view point and also from the view point of mechanism of amino acid metabolism. Specific metabolic role of amino acids includes biosynthesis of polypeptides and proteins and synthesis of nucleotides¹. However, metallic ions play a significant role in the oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids. Kinetics of oxidation of amino acids by a variety of oxidants like Mn^{III}², Co^{III}³, Os^{VIII}, Fe(CN)₆³⁻⁴, chloramine-T⁵, 1-chlorobenzotriazole⁶, *N*-bromosuccinamide^{7,8} and *N*-bromobenzenesulphonamide⁹ in both acid and alkaline media have been studied. However, various types of the reaction models have been suggested but the specific details are yet to be found out. Also there are still controversies regarding the oxidation products of α amino acids, as α keto acids are reported^{10,11} both as intermediates and also the oxidation products. In most of the reactions, the end products are the aldehydes¹², the intermediate $\text{R-CH=N}^+\text{H}_2$ undergoes hydrolysis to yield aldehyde

whereas its interaction with the oxidant yields nitrile. However evidence has yet been adduced to confirm the presence of such an imine intermediate.

The oxidizing potentialities of cerium(IV) in H₂SO₄ medium have conclusively been established¹³⁻¹⁵ and the oxidant exists in the form of sulphato species. Nevertheless, the oxidant has rarely been employed in perchloric acid medium probably owing to the presence of dimers and polymers of Ce^{IV}¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Although, the concentration of such dimers and polymers are significantly less, their contribution to the overall rate of reaction can not be neglected in higher concentration of Ce^{IV}.

These were certain observations that prompted us to undertake the title study.

Results and discussion

The concentration of cerium(IV) was varied from 4.3×10^{-4} to 2.4×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ at $[\text{H}^+] = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³, $[\text{Lys}] = 1 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³ for uncatalyzed reaction. Pseudo-first order plots were made and pseudo-first

order rate constant (k') were found to be independent of concentration of Ce^{IV} . For catalyzed reaction, the concentration of cerium(IV) was varied from 4.3×10^{-4} to 2.4×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} at different concentration of lysine viz. 1.0×10^{-2} , 2.0×10^{-2} , 3.0×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} respectively at $[H^+] = 1.0$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Ag^+] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} and temp. = 45 °C. The first order rate constants (k') in silver(I) catalysed reaction were also independent of the initial cerium(IV) concentration (Table 1).

The concentration of lysine was varied from 5.0×10^{-3} to 5.0×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} at $[Ce^{IV}] = 5.7 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[H^+] = 1.0$ mol dm^{-3} for uncatalyzed reaction. The plot of pseudo-first order rate constant vs $[Lys]$ yielded a straight line passing through the origin indicating first order dependence with respect to amino acid. The concentration of lysine in Ag^+ catalyzed reaction was varied from 5.0×10^{-3} to 5.0×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} at fixed conc. of $[H^+] = 1.0$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Ag^+] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} and temp. = 45 °C at three conc. of cerium(IV) viz. 5.7×10^{-4} , 1.42×10^{-3} and 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} respectively. The order with respect to lysine is also one in catalyzed reaction (Table 1).

The hydrogen ion conc. was varied from 0.25 to 1.5 mol dm^{-3} at $[Ce^{IV}] = 5.7 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Lys] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} . The rate initially increases and then tends towards a limiting value with increasing hydrogen ion concentration in uncatalyzed reaction.

Similarly in case of Ag^+ catalyzed reaction the hydrogen ion conc. was varied from 0.5 to 2.5 mol dm^{-3} employing perchloric acid at fixed conc. of $[Ce^{IV}] = 5.7 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Lys] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} and $[Ag^+] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} at three temperatures viz 40, 45 and 50 °C respectively. First order rate constants increases with increasing concentration of hydrogen ion.

The effect of ionic strength on the rate of reaction was also studied employing sodium perchlorate at fixed conc. of $[Ce^{IV}] = 5.7 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Lys] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} and $[H^+] = 1.0$ mol dm^{-3} . The rate of reaction slightly increases with increasing ionic strength. However, the rate was independent of ionic strength in silver(I) catalysed reaction.

The conc. of silver(I) was varied from 1.0×10^{-4} to 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} at $[Ce^{IV}] = 5.7 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Lys] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} and $[H^+] = 1.0$ mol dm^{-3} . A plot of rate against $[Ag^+]$ yields a straight line with non zero intercept that conforms to a simultaneous uncatalyzed reaction.

Table 1 Pseudo-first order and second order rate constant for the reaction of $[Lys]$ and $[Ce^{IV}]$ in $HClO_4$ medium
 $[Ag^+] = 5 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[H^+] = 1.0$ mol dm^{-3} ,
 Temp = 45 °C

$10^4 [Ce^{IV}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^2 [Lys]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^4 (k')$ (s^{-1})	$10^5 (k)$ ($dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$)
4.3	1.0	3.38	1.45
5.7	1.0	2.60	1.48
8.5	1.0	1.92	1.63
14.2	1.0	1.15	1.63
17.5	1.0	0.95	1.66
20.0	1.0	0.83	1.66
24.0	1.0	0.70	1.68
4.3	2.0	6.76	1.45
5.7	2.0	5.20	1.48
8.5	2.0	3.85	1.63
14.2	2.0	2.30	1.63
17.5	2.0	1.90	1.66
20.0	2.0	1.66	1.66
24.0	2.0	1.40	1.68
4.3	3.0	10.1	1.45
5.7	3.0	7.80	1.48
8.5	3.0	5.70	1.61
14.2	3.0	3.45	1.63
17.5	3.0	2.90	1.69
20.0	3.0	2.49	1.66
24.0	3.0	2.10	1.68
5.7	0.50	1.30	1.48
5.7	0.75	1.95	1.48
5.7	1.0	2.6	1.48
5.7	1.5	3.2	1.48
5.7	2.0	5.2	1.48
5.7	3.0	7.8	1.48
5.7	4.0	10.5	1.49
5.7	5.0	13.0	1.48
14.2	0.50	0.580	1.64
14.2	0.75	0.864	1.63
14.2	1.0	1.15	1.63
14.2	1.5	1.73	1.63
14.2	2.0	2.30	1.63
14.2	3.0	3.45	1.63
14.2	4.0	4.6	1.63
14.2	5.0	5.75	1.63
20.0	0.50	0.415	1.64
20.0	0.75	0.625	1.65
20.0	1.0	0.830	1.66
20.0	1.5	1.25	1.66
20.0	2.0	1.66	1.66
20.0	3.0	2.49	1.66
20.0	4.0	3.35	1.67
20.0	5.0	4.15	1.66

The reactions of cerium(IV) in $HClO_4$ medium proceed much faster than the reaction in sulphate medium. Kinetic investigations of oxidation by

cerium(IV) have been carried out extensively in sulphuric acid medium and sulphato complexes such as $CeSO_4^{2+}$, $Ce(SO_4)_2$ and $Ce(SO_4)_3^{2-}$ have been established and quantified¹⁹. However, cerium(IV) in perchloric acid medium does not indicate complex formation although Ce^{4+} , $Ce(OH)^{3+}$, $(Ce-O-Ce)^{6+}$ and $(HO-Ce-O-CeOH)^{4+}$ species of cerium(IV) are well established²⁰.

Cerium(IV) in acid perchlorate medium exists predominantly in the monomeric form such as Ce^{4+} and its hydrolyzed forms, $[CeOH^{3+}]$ and $[Ce(OH)_2^{2+}]$ apart from the dimeric and polymeric forms. The polymeric species are significantly less than the dimeric species in acidic solution of cerium(IV) concentration.

However, several values of hydrolysis constant (K_h) of cerium(IV) are available in the literature. McAuley *et al.*²¹ determined K_h to be $0.2 \pm 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 25 °C which is compared well with the values of 0.18 (25 °C) and 0.11 (5 °C) reported by Offner and Skoog²². However, the value of K_h determined kinetically in this work is 0.5 mol dm^{-3} which agreed well with these values. Since the rate increases with increasing hydrogen ion concentration, Ce^{4+} should be more reactive species than its hydrolyzed form.

Further, the amino acids are known to exist in zwitter ionic form in equilibrium with anionic and cationic forms depending upon the pH of the solution. Since the concentration of the hydrogen ion employed in the reaction is sufficiently high, the lysine in view of its pK values should predominantly be in the cationic forms.

where $R = CH_2(CH_2)_3-NH_2$

Amino acids are reported³ to form an adduct with Ag^I owing to availability of electron pair on oxygen atom²³. Therefore, an adduct between Ag^I and lysine is initially formed that on further interaction with Ce^{IV} yields another adduct of higher valent silver. Thus considering first order with respect to cerium(IV) and lysine each and also simultaneous uncatalyzed reaction and in presence of silver(I), the following reaction mechanism consisting of steps (2) to (7) can be proposed.

The proposed mechanism leads to the rate law (8) accounting for an experimental observation

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = \left[\frac{k'_1 K'_1 [H^+]}{(K_h + [H^+])(1 + K'_1 [Lys])} + \frac{k'_2 K'_2 [Ag^I][H^+]}{(K_h + [H^+])(1 + K'_2 [Lys])} \right] [Ce^{4+}][Lys] \quad (8)$$

Since the order with respect to lysine is one, the inequality in terms, viz. $1 \gg K'_1 [Lys]$, $1 \gg K'_2 [Lys]$ in the denominator of the eq. (8) is valid. This reduces the rate law (8) to (9)

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = \left[\frac{k'_1 K'_1 [H^+]}{(K_h + [H^+])} + \frac{k'_2 K'_2 [Ag^I][H^+]}{(K_h + [H^+])} \right] [Ce^{4+}][Lys] \quad (9)$$

$$k(K_h + [H^+]) = k'_1 K'_1 [H^+] + k'_2 K'_2 [Ag^I][H^+] \quad (10)$$

Since equilibrium constants in the rate eq. (10) are small, eq. (10) can be further reduced to eq. (11)

$$k(K_h + [H^+]) = k_1 [H^+] + k_2 [Ag^I][H^+] \quad (11)$$

where $k_1 = k'_1 K'_1$, $k_2 = k'_2 K'_2$ and k is an observed second order rate constant.

A plot of $k(K_h + [H^+]) / [H^+]$ versus $[Ag^I]$ was made from the eq. (11), a straight line with non zero intercept was obtained (Fig. 1). k_1 and k_2 were calculated from the intercept and slope and found to be $7.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $3.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. The values of such constants are comparable to

previously reported values for oxidation of other amino acids in similar experimental conditions^{24,25}.

Fig. 1. A plot of $k(K_h + [H^+])/[H^+]$ vs Ag^I .

So far as the transfer of electron from the substrate to the oxidant is concerned, the detailed analytical mode of the reaction events can be given as Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The complexation of silver(I) through nitrogen of the amino group of lysine was ruled out on the premise that the interaction of an electron deficient metal ion with the nitrogen of the protonated amine group is not a reasonable proposition.

Experimental

The kinetic studies of oxidation of lysine by Ce^{IV} in perchloric acid medium has been studied by monitoring Ce^{IV} . The solution of ceric perchlorate was prepared by dissolving ceric ammonium nitrate (B.D.H., AnalaR) in perchloric acid (E. Merck) and solution was

standardized by titrating aliquot of the test solution against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate (E. Merck) solution employing ferroin as an indicator. The titration was always done in the presence of H_2SO_4 to obtain clear and stable colour change at the end point. All other reagents were of AnalaR reagent grade and were used as supplied. Doubly-distilled water was employed throughout the study.

Kinetic measurements :

The reactions were carried out in stoppered flasks at 45 ± 0.1 °C. All the ingredients of the reaction mixture except Ce^{IV} were taken in the flasks and reaction was initiated by adding a known volume of ceric perchlorate solution. An aliquot (5 cm³) of the reaction mixture was withdrawn periodically. The aliquot was added to ice-cooled dil. H_2SO_4 (~1.0 mol dm³) and Ce^{IV} was titrated against the standard solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin as indicator. Initial rates were measured employing plane mirror method. Pseudo-first order plots were made wherever reaction conditions permitted. Triplicate rate measurements were reproducible to within $\pm 1\%$.

Since most of the kinetics of the reaction were studied under pseudo-first order conditions, the stoichiometry of the reaction was determined only in reactions with excess of lysine over Ce^{IV} . Such reactions were allowed to occur in a thermostated water bath at 45 ± 0.1 °C for 24 h, when the Ce^{IV} was completely utilized and were tested for the presence of both nitrile and aldehyde, the products usually reported in the oxidation of amino acids. Nitrile tests were negative. The qualitative tests of aldehyde were positive. Therefore the stoichiometry of the reaction based on the formation of an aldehyde can be represented by equation :

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References

1. H. D Jakubke and H. Jersekheit, "Amino Acids, Peptides and Proteins", Wiley, New York, 1977; H. C. Freeman, *Adv. Protein Chem.*, 1967, 22, 258.

2. M. A. Beg and Kamaliddin, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 1167.
3. A. V. Usha, B. Sethuram and T. N. Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 528.
4. S. K. Upadhyay and M. C. Aggrawal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 416.
5. A. Kumar, A. K. Bose and S. P. Mushaan, *M. S. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 106; D. S. Mahadevappa, K. S. Rangappa and N. M. M. Gowda, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 3651.
6. R. C. Hiremath, J. M. Mayanna and N. Venkatsubramaniam, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1987, 1569.
7. G. Gopalakrishnan and J. H. Hogg, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1985, **50**, 1206.
8. G. Chandra and S. N. Shrivastava, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 773.
9. Puttaswami N. Vaz, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 2001, **113**, 325.
10. B. T. Gowda and D. S. Mahadevappa, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1983, 323.
11. D. Laloo and M. K. Mahanti, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1990, 311.
12. Indu Rao, Seema Jain and P. D. Sharma, *Int. J. Chem. Kinetics*, 1992.
13. T. J. Kemp, "Comprehensive Chem. Kinetics", eds. C. H. Bamford and C. H. F. Tipper, Elsevier, 1972, **7**, 274.
14. A. McAuley, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 245.
15. K. Kumar, A. Nowduri and V. Parvataneni, *Acta Chem. Slov.*, 2008, **55**, 425.
16. K. P. Lawrier and T. Steemers, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1976, **12**, 185.
17. A. Samuni and G. Czapski, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 487.
18. J. Prasad, J. Singh and R. A. Singh, *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*, 2006.
19. J. I. Morrow and G. W. Shreees, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 2606.
20. W. H. Richardson in "Oxidation in Organic Chem.", ed. K. B. Wibug, Academic, New York, 1965, Chap. 4.
21. J. Amzad and A. McAuley, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans. 1*, 1974, 252.
22. H. G. Offner and D. A. Skoog, *Anal. Chem.*, 1966, **38**, 1520.
23. A. D. E. Pullin and J. M. C. Pollock, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, **54**, 11.
24. V. Devra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 290.
25. Indu Sharma, V. Devra, D. Gupta, C. M. Gangwal and P. D. Sharma, *Int. J. Chem. Kinetics*, 1995, **7**.